

INTERTEXTUALITY AS A SIGNIFICANT CONCEPT

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Abstract. *There are numerous terms that are used within various branches of linguistics as well as Literature and most of them are needed to be analyzed during the learning process in order to be aware of the real meaning of this and that term to use them correctly in explanations and one of the terms that are used in most fields including Linguistics, Literature as well Translation study is Intertextuality.*

Keywords: *Intertextuality, plagiarism, literature, fiction, poetry, texts, references, used words, author, reader.*

Human beings have not only been living to survive but also keeping in touch with the people around by communicating, expressing his or her feelings, wishes and other needs in the seek of better life, guidance towards the right path and more often help which make people have dialogues among them and that's to say, one cannot live in society without keeping contact with others.

It is evident that individuals have been in relationship with each other since the dawn of time and trying to express themselves in the various means of tools and expressions which resulted with the coming out of plethora of languages and have been spoken during the whole era and those languages are full of the usage of more and more different and new terms that require being analyzed within various fields such as linguistics, literature, translation study, linguoculturalogy with both simple and more complex approaches. One of them is the term Intertextuality.

Intertextuality is the shaping of the meaning of a text by another text, either through deliberate compositional strategies such as quotation, allusion, plagiarism, translation, or through relationships between similar or related works perceived by the audience or reader of the text. These references are sometimes make intentional and depend on the reader's prior knowledge and understanding of the referent, but the effect of intertextuality is not always intentional and sometimes unintentional and therefore, associated with strategies used by writers working in creative genres (fiction, poetry, drama, and even unwritten texts such as performance and digital media) and intertextuality can now be understood as an integral part of any text. While reading this description, there is a question that comes to the mind first is that why one is supposed to understand the importance of Intertextuality in Literature. Well, Intertextuality is a fundamental concept in literature and the arts that refers to the intricate web of connections between different texts. Understanding intertextuality enriches the experience of engaging with a work of art or literature, allowing readers or viewers to uncover hidden depths and nuanced perspectives.

In other words, while creating a new work, writers usually address to the works already written by another writers or just borrow from those previous texts, and their works acquire layers of meanings.

In addition, when a text is read in the light of another text, all the assumptions and effects of the other text give a new meaning and influence to readers by the way of interpreting the original text.

But intertextuality also brings pleasure to readers since it is nice to find something familiar in the text, to guess what this or that episode is connected with, where the author took this phrase from. Such recognition is also pleasant because one feels involved in the creation of the work,

because this is precisely the recognition that the author is not only like-minded but also it means that he read the same authors, noticed the same ideas in their works as the person who is reading his or her book.

On the other hand, there are some misunderstandings which require one to distinguish the differences between Intertextuality and plagiarism.

Well, different words, ideas or thoughts can be used in order to enrich one's work with facts, colorful ideas or opinions and of course a writer gives references to those given words or ideas where they have been taken from and as a result it can be called Intertextuality not plagiarism as everything is mentioned accurately in forms of references or mini dictionary below, differ from intertextuality, using somebody else's words or ideas as own, without giving credit to the original source, is called plagiarism and in each field it is recommended to check own created work for plagiarism.

All and all, we can conclude that Intertextuality and plagiarism differ from each other with mentioning the address for the derived information or just acting as if they were the only author and not giving any explanation about the used data.

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